

MORFEO and LIFT: are you allergic to petals?

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ABSTRACT

Adaptive optics–assisted observations with the ELT require tight control of phasing errors. In particular, the petal modes associated with the segmented structure of the ELT’s M4 deformable mirror can significantly degrade AO performance if left uncorrected. However, during astronomical observations, the telescope does not provide a dedicated facility for sensing these so-called petal errors, which can be introduced by effects such as low wind or other internal and external disturbances. MORFEO (Multi-conjugate adaptive Optics Relay For ELT Observations, formerly MAORY) addresses this issue by implementing a strategy to sense and correct petal-like aberrations. This is achieved by equipping the full-aperture infrared wavefront sensor with an optical device that generates a defocused image in a narrow, quasi-monochromatic band. The resulting configuration enables the application of focal-plane wavefront sensing techniques to estimate low-order modes, including the critical petal terms. The baseline solution for this functionality is the use of LIFT (Linearized Focal-plane Technique). In this work, we present the design and implementation of this approach, along with simulation results that evaluate its expected performance. One of the main challenges is the limited capture range of the sensing technique. To address this, we explore a multi-band configuration that distributes different spectral bands across the three natural guide star wavefront sensors of MORFEO.

Keywords: Extremely Large Telescope, MORFEO, Petaling, Wavefront Sensing, LIFT, Adaptive Optics

1. INTRODUCTION

On the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT), there is the risk to undergo the so-called “petaling” effect, that is wavefront discontinuities between portions of the pupil (delimited by the spider shadows) which turn into differential pistons during the Adaptive Optics (AO) correction. There are currently two identified causes for the wavefront discontinuities:

- strong atmospheric residuals that lead to a decorrelation between one side of a spider arm and the other;
- the Low Wind Effect (LWE), already observed on the Very Large Telescope (VLT) [1] and in particular with the SPHERE instrument. It comes from a temperature difference between one side of a spider arm and the other due to poor heat exchange in low wind conditions.

Whether the discontinuities turn into differential pistons also depends on the AO system and its control strategy. MORFEO (Multi-conjugate adaptive Optics Relay for For ELT Observations) [2] is little sensitive to the first cause, as the Multi-Conjugate AO (MCAO) reconstruction is limited to continuous wavefronts thanks to a regularization based on the turbulence statistics. However the LWE can create discontinuities of the order of

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several microns that are uncorrelated with the turbulence and lead to strong differential pistons even in the framework of MORFEO. Although the telescope is not supposed to observe in low wind conditions, it is foreseen that some observations will happen in these conditions anyway (as it does on the VLT). Moreover the phasing state of the telescope - especially the deformable mirror M4 - is not completely guaranteed at handover. The specified wavefront error at handover is 200 nm RMS, meaning that we could have some residual differential pistons of the order of a few hundreds of nm. Those errors are not well seen by the MCAO sensors and thus cannot be corrected with MORFEO in its preliminary design.

In order to estimate differential pistons, various solutions have been proposed and have been or are being tested at different levels, for example: focal plane wavefront sensing [3, 4], Holographic Dispersed Fringe Sensor [5], Zernike sensor [6], rotational shearing interferometer [7]... Among those, focal plane wavefront sensing offers the advantage of a very simple hardware implementation, hence it was chosen as a mitigation solution for MORFEO to minimize the impact on the opto-mechanical design. A defocused Point Spread Function (PSF) will be produced in some of the Natural Guide Star (NGS) wavefront sensors and the LIFT (LInearized Focal Plane Technique) algorithm [8, 9] will be run to estimate the so-called petals.

In this proceeding, we show results of LIFT simulations in the context of MORFEO. The simulations are based on realistic residual phase screens from end-to-end (E2E) simulations including the full MCAO correction. We first present the foreseen optical design to introduce the defocused PSF and the chosen design parameters based on Monte-Carlo simulations. Then, we present some performance results both with small piston errors (few 100 nm) and with large piston errors (1-2 μm).

2. LIFT DESIGN

MORFEO features two 1×1 and one 2×2 Shack-Hartmann sensors called the Low Order (LO). Although the petal signal can be retrieved from the 2×2 LO sensor [10, 11], we have found that the estimation is less robust than with a defocused full aperture PSF. Hence LIFT will be used on the two 1×1 sensors, which normally only measure tip/tilt. To benefit from the AO correction, it will work in H band. To divide the flux between LIFT and the in-focus tip/tilt PSF, we chose a narrow band instead of a simple split. This presents two advantages with respect to a simple flux split on the LO band:

- LIFT works in quasi-monochromatic conditions, which simplifies the model.
- We can use two different wavelengths on the two 1×1 LO for phase unwrapping.

2.1 Optical design

A zoom on the optical design of the 1×1 LO is shown in Fig. 1. The fold mirror before the focusing lens was replaced by a notch dichroic that reflects most of the sensor's band on the front face, and about 10% of the H band on the back face. The back face reflected beam arrives with a shift and a defocus in the focal plane, so that the LIFT spot is imaged on the same detector. The back face is slightly curved to introduce the defocus, and its coating changes from one wavefront sensor to another in order to select a different wavelength.

Figure 1: LO 1×1 design with additional defocused PSF (magenta rays) to run LIFT.

2.2 Design parameters

The choice of the two wavelengths is a trade-off between capture range and robustness. The capture range is $\pm\Lambda/2$ with Λ the beating wavelength, given by:

$$\Lambda = \frac{\lambda_1 \lambda_2}{|\lambda_1 - \lambda_2|} \quad (1)$$

The closer the wavelengths, the greater the capture range. On the other hand, an error greater or equal to $|\lambda_1 - \lambda_2|/2$ on the single wavelength estimation leads to an unwrapping error. We chose to prioritize robustness and thus selected wavelengths at the extrema of the H band: 1505 nm and 1750 nm. This provides a capture range of about $\pm 5\mu\text{m}$.

Then, the two main design parameters for each single LIFT are the PSF sampling and the defocus offset amplitude. Given the relatively small difference between the two wavelengths, we refer to the sampling ratio and the defocus in radians at an intermediate wavelength of 1635 nm. The sampling is then scaled with the wavelength, but the defocus is kept equal in terms of optical path difference. Our initial guess for these parameters is a sampling of 0.6 Nyquist (1.2 pixels per λ/D) and a defocus offset of 1.8 rad RMS (468 nm RMS). This choice is driven by two aspects: the AO residuals and the flux. The correction level is low in the technical Field of View (FoV), i. e. the Strehl ratio is between 5 and 20%, and the larger defocus provides more robustness. However, it also spreads the PSF more and the flux is already quite low. This is partially compensated by a rougher sampling. We explored the range 0.5 - 1 Nyquist for the sampling and 1.2 - 2.2 rad (312 - 572 nm) for the defocus in Monte-Carlo simulations, considering an exposure time of 1 second. We simulated long exposure open-loop PSFs using spatial power spectral densities of the phase residuals derived from E2E simulations in median conditions (seeing = 0.644", $z = 30$ deg, $L_0 = 25$ m, Cn2 profile from ESO specifications). The analysis confirmed that a low sampling, close to 0.5 Nyquist, is preferable. In our case, we maintain the sampling at 0.6 Nyquist (at 1635 nm) to avoid a too rough sampling for the tip/tilt PSF. However, a lower defocus offset would be beneficial. A defocus offset of 416 nm seems a good trade-off for the range 65" - 80", which represents most of the technical FoV area, though it performs worse at 55". To summarize, we select the following design parameters for LIFT:

- Focus offset: 416 nm RMS
- Pixel size: 7.3 mas (0.6 Nyquist at 1635 nm)
- Sensing wavelengths (on two different stars): 1505 nm and 1750 nm

3. CLOSED-LOOP SIMULATIONS WITH PETALS

3.1 Monochromatic range

In this section, we assume that the petals to estimate are within the range given by the single wavelength ($[-\lambda/2, +\lambda/2]$) and the petal command is derived from the average of the two sensors' estimations. The petal pattern is always the following: [0, 400, 100, -300, -400, 200] nm (Fig. 2). In these simulations, the AO residuals come from a 30-second E2E simulation including the Reference loop in median conditions. The additional WaveFront Error (WFE) on these AO residuals due to the chosen petal pattern is 270 nm RMS. In the following, the figure of merit is the difference of WFE between the initial residuals and the petaled residuals corrected with LIFT in closed loop, averaged on the last 15 seconds of simulations. The simulations were performed with a defocus offset of 468 nm instead of 416 nm. In addition, we always use an integrator gain of 0.1 and a frame rate of 1 Hz without trying to optimize the loop parameters. Hence, the results presented here are slightly pessimistic.

Figure 2: Petal pattern used in the simulations ($[0, 400, 100, -300, -400, 200]$ nm, clockwise). The segment at 7 o'clock is at 0 nm and is considered as the reference.

3.1.1 Good case

As a reference, we first report a simulation in good conditions, i. e. with two stars of magnitude $H = 16$ at $55''$ off-axis (with angles 0 deg and 120 deg). We plot the WFE as a function of time for the initial AO residuals, the same residuals with the additional petal pattern and the residuals with LIFT's correction (Fig. 3). The difference in quadrature between the final WFE and the original, averaged on the last 15 seconds, is 25 nm. The petal error was thus efficiently corrected. We note that the correction of the petals sometimes improves the overall WFE (e. g. around 17 seconds). Indeed the MCAO residuals are continuous but they do present some differential piston, at the level of a few tens of nm.

Figure 3: Closed loop correction of a petal pattern with LIFT on two stars of magnitude $H = 16$ at $55''$ off axis (at 0 deg and 120 deg). Black: Original MORFEO residuals without petal. Red: MORFEO residuals with petal pattern applied. Blue: Closed loop correction with LIFT (frame rate = 1 Hz, integrator gain = 0.1). The differential WFE between the blue and black curve is 25 nm in average over the last 15 seconds.

3.1.2 Performance as a function of distance

We plot the residual petal WFE as a function of the stars' off-axis distance in a bright case ($H = 16$), for two NGSs at 0 deg and 120 deg or one NGS at 0 deg (Fig. 4). With two NGSs, the performance is good (30 - 35 nm) up to $65''$, and slowly degrades to about 65 nm at the edge of the FoV. However, with only one NGS, we suffer more from anisoplanatism effects and the petal residual is already at 80 nm at $55''$. It then quickly increases to more than 100 nm for larger distances.

Figure 4: Residual piston WFE as a function of the off-axis distance for two NGSs (top) or one NGS (bottom). The error bars correspond to the standard deviation on 5 noise occurrences.

3.1.3 Performance as a function of flux

We plot the residual petal WFE as a function of the stars' H magnitude when the stars are at the edge of the technical FoV ($80''$), for two NGSs at 0 deg and 120 deg or one NGS at 0 deg (Fig. 5). The simulations were limited to a magnitude of 18.5, as the loop diverges at $H = 19$ for the chosen frame rate and gain.

Figure 5: Residual piston WFE as a function of the H magnitude for two NGSs (top) or one NGS (bottom). The error bars correspond to the standard deviation on 5 noise occurrences.

3.2 Large petals

In this section, we investigate the ability to efficiently unwrap the piston from the estimation on the two NGSs at different wavelengths. We consider piston values that actually need unwrapping for the assumed sensing wavelengths (i. e. the piston is larger than $\lambda/2$). In this case, we simply multiply the petal pattern from the monochromatic case by 3: $[0, 1200, 300, -900, -1200, 600]$ nm.

3.2.1 Unwrapping method

The method used for unwrapping is a matching with the expected measurements on the capture range ($[-5\mu m, +5\mu m]$), considering an interval around each measurement of ± 50 nm to account for measurement noise (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Dual-wavelength matching algorithm principle for an input piston of 1800 nm and two measurements at 1505 nm and 1750 nm. The blue and green curves correspond to the expected measurements at the two wavelengths. The dashed horizontal lines correspond to the wrapped measurements ± 50 nm. The vertical bands correspond to the potential unwrapped candidates for the two wavelengths. They overlap at 1800 nm, where the two wrapped measurements match the expected ones for that input piston. The research range was reduced for better display.

3.2.2 Results

We show the result of a simulation in good conditions (two stars of $H = 16$, distance $55''$) in Fig. 7. The correction is poor and quite unstable. While more work can be done to optimize the loop, it is important to note that we do not only suffer from noise but also from anisoplanatism, which impacts the unwrapping as the two wavelengths are on two different stars. Indeed, the atmospheric residuals affect the measurement similarly to aliasing because the petal mode correlates with all spatial frequencies. If the residuals are different in the line of sight of the two stars, the unwrapping method, which relies on the difference between the two measurements, is likely to choose the wrong period and thus introduce an error of a multiple of the wavelength. A fundamental assumption of these simulations is that the anisoplanatism effects average out on a time scale of one second, but we see that this is not the case with the AO residuals used here. To show this, we ran the same simulation using perfect petal sensors, which directly measure the average phase in a segment, and though the correction is much more stable, we still have a residual piston WFE of about 475 nm (Fig. 8). In particular, one segment (green) tends to converge towards an offset of approximately one wavelength (considering the average of the two) with respect to the input piston.

The simplest way to remove the anisoplanatism effects would be to have the two wavelengths on each sensor. This way, the two wavelengths see the same residuals and the two measurement have the same bias, leading to a correct unwrapping. Simulations with perfect petal sensors do provide good results in that case. However, that means a complex design for LIFT, with twice less flux available for each PSF, hence even more measurement noise. Looking at the piston commands, it does seem that we could have a good correction with a more robust unwrapping method. Averaging several piston estimations should also help remove the anisoplanatism effect. This will be investigated in future works.

Figure 7: Simulation with a large petal pattern and the multi-wavelength unwrapping in good conditions (two stars of magnitude $H = 16$ at $55''$ off axis). Top: Piston commands applied. Each colour corresponds to a segment. Dashed lines: pistons from the petal pattern. Bottom: Residual WFE. Black: Original MORFEO residuals without petal. Red: MORFEO residuals with petal pattern applied. Blue: Closed loop correction with LIFT (frame rate = 1 Hz, integrator gain = 0.1).

Figure 8: Same as Fig. 7 but with perfect petal sensors instead of LIFT.

4. CONCLUSION

We have identified LIFT as a good candidate to estimate the petals at the level of the LO sensors. In particular, it has the advantage of being easily implemented in the design of the 1×1 LO. The trade-off on its design parameters suggest a sampling of 7.3 mas/pixel and a focus offset of 416 nm. The two LIFT should work at two different wavelengths, 1505 nm and 1750 nm, to provide the ability to unwrap large differential pistons. Simulations show that, considering petals within the capture range of the single wavelength in H band, LIFT can provide a correction level down to 25 nm of residual petal WFE in good conditions, i. e. assuming two bright stars ($H = 16$) close to the scientific FoV ($55''$). The correction level stays good (less than 65 nm residual) down to $H = 18$ at the edge of the FoV ($80''$). However, if only one star is available, we can expect a residual of more than 100 nm in most cases. When the petals are larger than the single wavelength's capture range, the correction is poor, even when considering perfect sensors (475 nm residual WFE). Indeed, though the loop rate is slow (1 Hz), we are still suffering from quasi-static anisoplanatism effects. We will investigate more robust methods for this case.

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